

blue ript.
8/1/3336 h

* 28

and TKM6 — were resistant to the disease under artificial inoculation.

Chemical control trials for 2 consecutive seasons showed that 3 sprays of carbendazim (0.05%), benomyl (0.05%), and Brestanol (0.1%) gave good disease control in the field.

Epidemiological adaptation by the rice blast pathogen during adverse weather

G. P. Singh, R. N. Singh, and Paromita Mukherjee, Plant Pathology Department, N. D. University of Agriculture and Technology, Rice Research Station (RRS), Masodha, Faizabad, U.P., India

During kharif 1979, dark-brown to blackish lesions were observed on the panicle-bearing and ensheathed lower internodes and nodes of the stems in plants of a susceptible local rice cultivar Tulsiphool at the Faizabad RRS. The lesions were either eye-shaped or irregular; the latter were more common on the panicle axis and below its base. Blurred brown blotches appeared on the sheath encasing the affected part of the stem. There was mycelial growth with abundant sporulation on the ensheathed lesions on nodes and internodes (see photo). The naked lesions rarely sporulated. In advanced stages the lesions on the sheath also sporulated underneath.

No breaking at the panicle base was seen.

Long sheaths encasing the nodes and internodes are a peculiar characteristic of Tulsiphool and appear to provide favorable conditions for the development of those symptoms. The disease appeared during the last 2 weeks of October when night temperatures were relatively mild and considerable dew collected on the leaves. The microclimate was therefore suitable for disease development in the ensheathed nodes and

internodes. The general weather during the growing season, however, was unusually dry and not favorable for blast development (see table).

The occurrence of the disease on highly susceptible cultivars such as Tulsiphool under adverse situations appears epidemiologically significant. However, the disease may only be regarded as a "sleeper disease" in Eastern U. P. because of the requirement of critical weather parameters for its development.

Monthly meteorological data, June to November 1979, at the Faizabad Rice Research Station, India.

Weather parameter	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov
Rainfall (mm.)	27.2	182.2	31.2	21.2	39.0	22.4
Rainy days (no.)	2	12	4	2	4	1
Relative humidity (%)	63	84	81	79	85	84
Max temp (°C)	38.7	33.7	34.6	35.7	33.5	32.0
Bright sunshine (h)	9.7	6.9	9.7	9.5	9.4	8.9

Incidence and chemical control of ufra in boro fields

Md. Montezar Rahman, N. R. Sharma, and S. A. Miah, Plant Pathology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

A survey of ufra disease on boro rice was conducted in the Dacca-Narayanganj-Demra Project area in 1979 because ufra had appeared on transplanted aman rice in that area in 1978. Skipping 1979, the disease reappeared in 1980 and affected about 1.2 ha of transplanted IR8 severely in boro (Nov to Apr). Eighty percent of the crop of the heavily infected patches was completely lost.

To reduce disease severity and yield

loss due to ufra, carbofuran 3G was soil incorporated in the mild ufra-infected portion. Reduction in disease spread and severity was observed in the treated plots compared with the control (see table).

The yields of the treated plots and the control differed significantly. Carbofuran 3G at 34 kg/ha appeared best in controlling ufra and reducing yield loss.

Yield and ufra severity in carbofuran-treated and control plots of IR8, Dacca, Bangladesh, 1980.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Ufra severity (%)
Control	1.43 b	5.67 b
17 kg carbofuran 3G/ha	1.69 b	4.67 ab
34 kg carbofuran 3G/ha	2.93 a	1.67 a

Mean of 3 replications. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of time of nitrogen application on weed growth and yield of dry-seeded rice

Nizam U. Ahmed, senior scientific officer, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh; and K. Moody, International Rice Research Institute

Different amounts of nitrogen were incorporated into the soil before planting and applied as topdressing to dry-seeded wetland IR36 rice to determine the effect of time of nitrogen application on weed growth and crop yield.

Some plots received no basal applica-

Ensheathed lesions on nodes and internodes, and blotches on the sheath encasing the affected part of the stem of the cultivar Tulsiphool, Faizabad, U. P., India.

tion of nitrogen but received 30 kg N/ha at 2 and 4 weeks after emergence (WE). Others received a basal nitrogen application of 10-40 kg N/ha and, at 4 WE, additional nitrogen needed to make the total amount 60 kg N/ha. At 8 WE, all plots received an additional 40 kg N/ha.

All plots received a total of 100 kg N/ha. Each plot was weeded 3 times: 2, 5, and 8 WE. Before each weeding, and at harvest, weeds were sampled from three quadrats (0.5 × 0.5 m/plot), counted, and weighed.

At 2 WE, no significant difference in weed count was observed, but the weight of weeds harvested from the plots that received a basal application of 40 kg N/ha was significantly higher than that of weeds harvested from the plots that received a basal application of 0 or 10 kg N/ha (see table). Plots with smaller amounts of basal fertilizer were easier to weed because the weeds, primarily grasses, were smaller and easier to distinguish from the rice.

Topdressing of nitrogen affected the weed count 5 WE. The number of

weeds in the plots that received 20 kg N/ha as a topdressing was significantly lower than that in the plots that had received 40-60 kg N/ha as a topdressing by 4 WE. Weed counts in the plots that received 30 kg N/ha as a topdressing were significantly lower than those in the plots topdressed with 60 kg N/ha (see table).

Weed counts and weights before the third weeding (8 WE) and at harvest were not affected by the different rates of nitrogen applied either basally or as a topdressing. The total number and weight of weeds sampled throughout crop growth were likewise not affected.

Weed counts and weights at 2 WE

and weed counts at 5 WE were further analyzed for trend comparisons. Linear responses were significant. At 2 WE, the parameters increased with the amount of nitrogen applied basally while at 5 WE, weed counts increased with the amount of nitrogen applied as a topdressing.

The yield from the plots that received no basal nitrogen was significantly higher than that from the plots that received 20 or 40 kg N/ha as a basal application. Thus, delay in application of fertilizer nitrogen until the first weeding resulted in a reduction in the initial weed growth and an increase in grain yield.

Number and weight of weeds^a at 2 and 5 weeks after crop emergence (WE) and rice yield as affected by rate and time of nitrogen application.

Basal	N application rate (kg/ha)			Weeds at 2 WE		Weeds at 5 WE		Rice yield (t/ha)	
	Topdressing	2 WE	4 WE	8 WE	No.	Wt (g/m ²)	No.		Wt (g/m ²)
0	30	30	40	115 a	20.0 b	193 a	112.0 a	3.3 a	
10	0	50	40	126 a	38.8 b	164 ab	16.2 a	3.2 ab	
20	0	40	40	165 a	57.6 ab	163 ab	88.0 a	2.6 b	
30	0	30	40	167 a	67.6 ab	98 bc	85.2 a	2.8 ab	
40	0	20	40	205 a	76.8 a	76 c	67.6 a	2.6 b	

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Weed control in dry-seeded rainfed banded rice and its residual effect on weed growth of the subsequent transplanted rice

Nizam U. Ahmed, senior scientific officer, and M. Zahidul Hoque, head, Rice Cropping Systems Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

One of the most important rainfed cropping patterns in Bangladesh is dry-seeded rice followed by transplanted rice. Hand weeding is the only means for controlling weeds in dry-seeded rice, but it is becoming expensive. Therefore, butachlor [N-(butoxymethyl)-2-chloro-2',6'-diethylacetanilide] was tested as an alternate means for controlling weeds in dry-seeded rice. Butachlor's residual effect on the weeds of the following transplanted rice was also determined.

Three treatments (see table) with three replications were put in a randomized complete block design. The land

Effect of weed control treatments on performance and weed weight of the first dry-seeded rainfed banded rice and residual effect on the number and weight of weeds of the subsequent transplanted rice crop. BRRI, 1980 aus-t. aman season.^a

Treatment ^b	Dry-seeded rice (BR6) aus 1980			Transplanted rice ^c (Nizersail) t. aman, 1980		
	Stand count (no./0.25 m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./0.25 m ²)	Weed wt (g/0.25 m ²) at harvest	Weed counts (no./0.25 m ²)	Weed wt (g/0.25 m ²)
	2 WE				4 WT	4 WT
Unweeded check	45.00 a	1.38 a	77.83 a	34.40 a	60.11 a	4.59 a
Butachlor 2.0 kg/ha, fb HW at 3 WE	25.33 b	1.28 a	67.37 a	10.48 b	73.67 a	4.43 a
Hand weeding 2, 5, and 8 WE	43.67 a	2.29 b	103.50 b	3.28 c	43.67 a	6.10 a

^aAv of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level. ^bfb = followed by, HW = hand weeding, WE = weeks after crop emergence, ^cWT = weeks after transplanting.

used had medium elevation, clay loam with 2.0% organic matter, and pH of 6.8. It was banded and accumulated at least 2 to 3 cm water to allow rice cultivation. After land preparation, seeds of BR6 were sown in rows 25 cm apart at the rate of 100 kg/ha. In the appropriate plots butachlor was sprayed before the germinating rain came. Fertilizers were applied at 80-60-40 kg N, P₂O₅, and K₂O per hectare. Land prepa-

ration for the second crop of transplanted rice was done plot by plot; no treatment was applied to this crop.

Rice stand count, panicle count, weed count, and weed weights were determined by taking random samples from two 0.5 × 0.5-m quadrats in each plot. Grain yields were determined by taking crop-cuts from 3 × 2 m of each plot.

At 2.0 kg/ha, butachlor gave excellent weed control. There were no weeds